

A Randomized Controlled Trial to Evaluate Effect of Prophylactic Antibiotics in High-Risk Patients Undergoing Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy

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Abstract

Aim: Prophylactic antibiotics in high-risk patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Methods: A randomized controlled trial study was conducted in the Department of General Surgery, MGM Medical College Kishanganj, Bihar, India from May 2019 to May 2020. Patient admitted for Laparoscopic cholecystectomy were randomized into two groups A (who did not receive prophylactic antibiotics) and B (those who received antibiotics).

Results: A total of 200 patients were included with Group A and B included 100 and 100 patients, respectively, with similar baseline demographic characteristics and preoperative indications for cholecystectomy. Surgical site infection occurred in 7 patients in group A and 2 patients in group B ($p=0.048$) respectively. All Surgical site infections were superficial and responded to conservative management only. None of the infected patients required intravenous therapy or hospitalization. Mean duration of hospital stay in patients not having received prophylactic antibiotics (Group A) approached significance ($p=0.07$) though the range (in days) was the same in both the groups.

Conclusion: Prophylactic antibiotics play an important role in the prevention of SSI in patients at high risk, undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Keywords: Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy, High Risk, Antibiotics Prophylaxis.

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Introduction:

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) carries an extremely low rate of postoperative infection compared with open cholecystectomy [1]. The average rate of SSIs for LC has been reported in the literature to be between 0.4% and 6.3%, which is lower

than rates reported for open cholecystectomy [1-3] Unlike for open cholecystectomy, many investigators have suggested that antimicrobial prophylaxis is probably unnecessary for LC patients because the infection rate for LC is already low, and the

use of prophylactic antibiotics does not decrease the rate of wound infections or other postoperative infection complications [1,4-8]. Also, these recent meta-analyses and systematic reviews have concluded that a prophylactic antibiotic for elective LCs in low-risk patients is not useful, but there were no results in high-risk patients [9]. Despite these studies on the topic, many other surgeons still use and recommend the administration of prophylactic antibiotics for LC in low-risk patients. Generally, preoperative single-dose cefazolin as a prophylactic antibiotic has been recommended and widely used in clean-contaminated surgeries such as cholecystectomy and biliary surgery to reduce SSI [10]. Hence the present research was undertaken with the aim to evaluate role of prophylactic antibiotics in high-risk patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Material and methods

A randomized controlled trial study was conducted in the Department of General Surgery, MGM Medical College Kishanganj, Bihar, India from May 2019 to May 2020

Inclusion criteria:

- Diagnosed case of cholelithiasis with any high-risk factor
- Age > 18 years

Exclusion criteria:

- Pregnant and lactating females.
- Patients requiring antibiotics for any other reason
- Immunocompromised patients
- Evidence of active cholangitis/pancreatitis
- Moribund patients
- A patient who did not consent for surgery
- On table preclusion of laparoscopic surgery

Definitions:

High-risk patients – These patients had one or many of the following

1. Age >70 years,
2. Obesity (BMI \geq 30)
3. Diabetes mellitus
4. Acute cholecystitis with cholelithiasis with or without its complication (mucocoele/empyema/gangrenous gall bladder).

Surgical site infection (SSI) was classified as superficial surgical site infection, deep surgical site infection and distant site infection.

1. A **superficial surgical site infection** was defined as erythema and/or purulent discharge from any of the port site, superficial to the fascia.
2. A **deep surgical site infection** was defined as erythema and/or purulent discharge present deep to the fascia or in the gall bladder fossa
3. A **distant site infection** was defined as any infection remote to the surgical site.

Methods

Patient admitted for LC from surgical outpatient or emergency were randomized into two groups A and B, on the basis of computer-generated randomization tables. Group A patients received no antibiotics preoperatively. Only oral analgesics, proton pump inhibitors and supportive treatment were advised in usual doses, and these patients were followed up during the entire period of their hospital stay. If antibiotics needed to be administered (on the basis of clinical or laboratory suspicion), it was not withheld, but the patient was then excluded from the study.

Group B patients received a single dose of intravenous antibiotic (first generation Cephalosporin- intravenous Cephazolin 1-2 grams/day) within \leq 60 minutes prior to the

surgery. These patients also received postoperative care, similar to Group A patients.

Culture from the suspected site of infection was to be collected aseptically. The area around the surgical wound was cleaned with 70% ethyl alcohol, and the exudate was collected from the depth of the wound using two sterile cotton swabs, one for Gram stain and another for culture. Utmost care was taken not to touch the surrounding tissues to prevent contamination of swab from endogenous resident flora.

The samples that were collected were sent to the laboratory immediately for processing, to avoid desiccation and to prevent the growth of some species at room temperature that may negate the detection of the true pathogens.

Statistical analysis:

Data were recorded in a pre-designed, standardized data collection proforma and later entered in Microsoft Excel 2013 sheet. It was analyzed using the statistical software SPSS version 25.0 (SPSS Inc. Chicago, IL, USA).

Results

A total number of 210 patients fulfilled the inclusion criteria. Of these three patients did not consent for participation in the study, and two patients were immunocompromised. Hence 205 patients were finally enrolled for

the study. However, three patients had to be converted to open cholecystectomy, and two patients had evidence of gall bladder malignancy. Hence these were also excluded as per the study protocol. Accordingly, 200 patients were finally included in the study.

Group A and B included 100 and 100 patients, respectively. Baseline demographic characteristics (Table 1) and preoperative indications for cholecystectomy (Table 2) were similar in both groups. Intra-operative details were also not statistically different in the two groups. (Table 3). Since our study included patients having one or more preoperative risk factors for the development of SSI, a detailed analysis of risk factor status was also done. There was no statistically significant difference as regards the risk factors in the study and control groups. (Table 4) Surgical site infection occurred in 7 patients in group A and 2 patients in group B ($p=0.048$) respectively. (Table 6) All SSIs were superficial and responded to conservative management only. None of the infected patients required intravenous therapy or hospitalization. Mean duration of hospital stay in patients not having received prophylactic antibiotics (Group A) approached significance ($p=0.07$) though the range (in days) was the same in both the groups. All patients developed superficial SSI of the epigastric port (Gall bladder extraction port).

Table 1: Demographic and preoperative details

		Group A	Group B
Age		55 (25-80)	57 (28-80)
Sex Ratio (M:F)		0.85 (46:54)	0.66 (40:60)
Address	Rural	70	64
	Urban	30	36

Table 2 :Indications of cholecystectomy

Indications	Group A	Group B
Chronic cholecystitis with cholelithiasis	35	52
Acute cholecystitis with cholelithiasis ± sequelae (mucocoele/ empyema gall bladder/ gangrene)	47	30
Polyp	4	4
Post pancreatitis	8	7
Post ERCP (Endoscopic Retrograde Cholangio Pancreaticography)	6	7

Table 3: Intra-operative details

		Group A (n=100)	Group B (n=100)	P value
Duration of surgery	Difficult dissection (>30 mins for Calots dissection)	18	21	0.662
	Previous upper abdominal surgery	10	6	0.36
Bile spillage		30	33	0.899
Drain insertion		42	40	0.861

Table 4: Risk factors

		Group A (n=100)	Group B (n=100)	P value
Duration of surgery	Difficult dissection (>30 mins for Calots dissection)	17	20	0.662
	Previous upper abdominal surgery	8	6	0.36
Bile spillage		25	25	0.899
Drain insertion		50	49	0.861

Table 5: Numbers of risk factor

Risk factor	Group A (n=100)	Group B (n=100)
One	47	49
Two	40	42
Three	10	7
Four	3	2

Table 6: Post-operative outcomes

SSI		Group A (n=100)	Group B (n=100)	P value
	Superficial	7 (7%)	2 (2%)	0.048*
	Deep	0	0	NA
	Distant	0	0	NA
Hospital stay (days) mean ± SD		2.42 ± 0.54	2.33 ± 0.57	0.071

Discussion

SSIs are a common performance metric in assessing the quality of health care. Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) recently recommended that only a single dose of preoperative antibiotics should be administered to patients undergoing clean-contaminated procedures based on data from a variety of surgical disciplines. Laparoscopic cholecystectomy is one such procedure, and we wished to see whether a single dose too was mandatory or not. This was done because a routine and indiscriminate use of antibiotics promoted the menace of antibiotic resistance and associated complications [11].

Studies in the past have evaluated the role of prophylactic antibiotics in surgeries of various organ systems [12-14] in various other biliary surgeries [15-18], the role of single versus multiple doses [10] and timing of administration of antibiotics [19-21]. To the best of our knowledge, however, no study which has evaluated the role of prophylactic antibiotics in patients undergoing LC has included all patients with risk factors.

This study includes 200 patients all with high-risk factors in whom 100 patients did not receive any prophylactic antibiotics, and this is in comparison to a recently published study [8] in whom prophylactic antibiotics were not given in only 50 patients, there is no mention about the presence and absence of high-risk factors in these 50 patients.

In our study, the study population randomized to receive or not receive prophylactic antibiotics had similar demographic, preoperative and intraoperative details (as evident from the non-significant p values) suggesting the uniformity in baseline characteristics.

Incidence of SSI was found to be low in our study in the groups which had received

prophylactic antibiotics. Similar results have been seen in other studies as well [22].

In our present study we had bile spillage in twenty-five patients in the study group and twenty-five patients in the control group, these include both, bile spillage during surgery, i.e. iatrogenic and due to primary pathology, for example, gangrenous/perforated gall bladder. As a routine, we did not perform bile culture because this method does not guarantee the preoperative identification of which patients have bactibilia. Our results are in accordance with the recently published article by Hui TT et al. [23] in which no SSI was noticed in gall bladder perforation.

Use of prophylactic antibiotics was recommended in all patients undergoing cholecystectomy [24] or to those over the age of 60 years or with a history of previous attacks of acute cholecystitis [25] in the 20th century. Later, however, several studies have proved that prophylactic antibiotics, not even a single dose [8] decrease the risk of SSI after laparoscopic cholecystectomy [26]. However, none of these studies had all patients with some of the other risk factors.

Mean duration of hospital stay in patients not having received prophylactic antibiotics (Group A) approached significance ($p=0.07$). This could only be by chance since the range of duration of hospital stay (in days) was the same in both the groups. The patient was usually discharged on the next day of surgery. However, in the majority of cases, it was the psyche of the patient that he is ill and requires further hospitalization that leads to a relatively longer duration of stay, instead of surgical reasons. Our results are consistent with the meta-analysis conducted by Choudhary, A et al. [27] in terms of hospital stay.

Conclusion

Prophylactic antibiotics play an important role in the prevention of SSI in patients at high risk, undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Incidence of SSI was found to be low in our study in the groups which had received prophylactic antibiotics.

References

1. Chang WT, Lee KT, Chuang SC, Wang SN, Kuo KK, Chen JS, et al. The impact of prophylactic antibiotics on postoperative infection complication in elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy: a prospective randomized study. *Am J Surg* 2006;191: 721-5.
2. Biscione FM, Couto RC, Pedrosa TM, Neto MC. Comparison of the risk of surgical site infection after laparoscopic cholecystectomy and open cholecystectomy. *Infect Control HospEpidemiol* 2007;28:1103-6.
3. McGuckin M, Shea JA, Schwartz JS. Infection and antimicrobial use in laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *Infect Control HospEpidemiol* 1999;20:624-6.
4. Koc M, Zulfikaroglu B, Kece C, Ozalp N. A prospective randomized study of prophylactic antibiotics in elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *SurgEndosc* 2003;17:1716-8.
5. Mahatharadol V. A reevaluation of antibiotic prophylaxis in laparoscopic cholecystectomy: a randomized controlled trial. *J Med Assoc Thai* 2001;84:105-8.
6. Yildiz B, Abbasoglu O, Tirnaksiz B, Hamaloglu E, Ozdemir A, Sayek I. Determinants of postoperative infection after laparoscopic cholecystectomy. *Hepatogastroenterology* 2009;56:589-92.
7. Higgins A, London J, Charland S, Ratzler E, Clark J, Haun W, et al. Prophylactic antibiotics for elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy: are they necessary? *Arch Surg* 1999;134:611-3.
8. Sharma N, Garg PK, Hadke NS, Choudhary D. Role of prophylactic antibiotics in laparoscopic cholecystectomy and risk factors for surgical site infection: a randomized controlled trial. *Surg Infect (Larchmt)* 2010;11:367-70.
9. Ruangsri S, Laohawiriyakamol S, Sunpa- weravong S, Mahattanobon S. The efficacy of cefazolin in reducing surgical site infection in laparoscopic cholecystectomy: a prospective randomized double-blind controlled trial. *SurgEndosc* 2015;29:874- 81.
10. Mangram AJ, Horan TC, Pearson ML, Silver LC, Jarvis WR. Guideline for prevention of surgical site infection, 1999. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) Hospital Infection Control Practices Advisory Committee. *Am J Infect Control* 1999;27:97-132.
11. Bratzler DW, Dellinger EP, Olsen KM, Perl TM, Auwaerter PG, Bolon MK, et al. Clinical practice guidelines for antimicrobial prophylaxis in surgery. *Am J Health Syst Pharm*.2013;70:195-283.
12. Lee MR, Paver R. Prophylactic antibiotics in dermatological surgery. *Australas J Dermatol*. 2016 May; 57(2): 83-91.
13. Balamohan SM, Sawhney R, Lang DM, CherabuddiK,VaradrajanaVV,Bernard SH, et al. Prophylactic antibiotics in head and neck free flap surgery: A novel protocol put to the test. *Am J Otolaryngol*.Nov-Dec 2019; 40(6): 102276.
14. Knight M, Chiocchia V, Parlett C, Arias OR, Hua X, Hinshaw K, et al. Prophylactic antibiotics in the prevention of infection after operative vaginal delivery (ANODE): a multicentre randomised controlled trial. *Lancet* 2019 Jun 15;393(10189):2395-2403.
15. Degrandi O, Buscail E, Martellotto S, Gronnier C, Collet D, Adam JP, et al.

- Perioperative antibiotherapy should replace prophylactic antibiotics in patients undergoing pancreaticoduodenectomy preceded by preoperative biliary drainage. *J Surg Oncol* 2019 Sep;120(4):639-645.
16. Kaufman Z, Engelberg M, Eliashiv A, Reiss R. Systemic prophylactic antibiotics in elective biliary surgery. *Arch Surg* 1984 Sep;119(9):1002-4.
 17. Olsson G, Arnelo U, Lundell L, Persson G, Tornqvist B, Enochsson L. The role of antibiotic prophylaxis in routine endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography investigations as assessed prospectively in a nationwide study cohort. *Scand J Gastroenterol* 2015 Jul;50(7):924-31.
 18. Shinagawa N, Tachi Y, Ishikawa S, Yura J. Prophylactic antibiotics for patients undergoing elective biliary tract surgery: a prospective randomized study of cefotiam and cefoperazone. *Jpn J Surg* 1987 Jan;17(1):1-8.
 19. Hawn MT, Richman JS, Vick CC, Deierhoi RJ, Graham LA, Henderson WG. Timing of surgical antibiotic prophylaxis and the risk of surgical site infection. *JAMA Surg* 2013 Jul;148(7):649-57.
 20. Classen DC, Evans RS, Pestotnik SL, Horn SD, Menlove RL, Burke JP. The timing of prophylactic administration of antibiotics and the risk of surgical-wound infection. *N Engl J Med* 1992 Jan 30;326(5):281-6.
 21. Krüger CM, Adam U, Adam T, Kramer A, Heidecke CD, Makowiec F, et al. Bacteremia in pancreatic surgery conclusions for perioperative antibiotic prophylaxis. *World J Gastroenterol* 2019 Nov 7;25(41):6238-6247.
 22. Sarkut P, Kilicturgay S, Aktas H, Ozen Y, Kaya E. Routine Use of Prophylactic Antibiotics during Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy Does Not Reduce the Risk of Surgical Site Infections. *Surg Infect (Larchmt)* 2017 Jul;18(5):603-609.
 23. Hui TT, Giurgiu DI, Margulies DR, Takagi S, Iida A, Phillips EH. Iatrogenic gallbladder perforation during laparoscopic cholecystectomy: etiology and sequelae. *Am Surg.* 1999; 65(10):944-948.
 24. Stubbs RS. Wound infection after cholecystectomy: a case for routine prophylaxis. *Ann R Coll Surg Engl.* 1983 Jan;65(1):30-1.
 25. Nielsen ML, Moesgaard F, Justesen T, Scheibel JH, Lindenberg S. Wound sepsis after elective cholecystectomy. Restriction of prophylactic antibiotics to risk groups. *Scand J Gastroenterol.* 1981; 16(7): 937-40.
 26. Dijk AHV, Hoek MVD, Rutgers M, Duijvendijk PV, Donkervoort SC, Reuver PRD, et al. Efficacy of Antibiotic Agents after Spill of Bile and Gallstones during Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy. *Surg Infect (Larchmt)* May/Jun 2019;20(4):298-304.
 27. Choudhary A, Bechtold ML, Puli SR, Othman MO, Roy PK. Role of prophylactic antibiotics in laparoscopic cholecystectomy: a meta-analysis. *J Gastrointest Surg.* 2008;12(11):1847-1853.